

Yttrium and lanthanide perchlorate complexes of 2,3-dimethyl-4-formyl-[2'-(aminomethyl)pyridine]-1-phenyl-3-pyrazoline-5-one and 2,3-dimethyl-4-formyl(benzhydrazide)-1-phenyl-3-pyrazolin-5-one

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Manuscript received 12 January 2009, revised 20 July 2009, accepted 20 August 2009

Abstract : Two series of complexes of two Schiff bases, 2,3-dimethyl-4-formyl-[2'-(aminomethyl)pyridine]-1-phenyl-3-pyrazolin-5-one (L_1) and 2,3-dimethyl-4-formyl(benzhydrazide)-1-phenyl-3-pyrazolin-5-one (L_2), with the general compositions $[\text{Ln}(\text{L}_1)_2(\text{ClO}_4)_2](\text{ClO}_4)$ and $[\text{Ln}(\text{L}_2)_2(\text{ClO}_4)](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ (where Ln = Y, La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd, Dy, Ho or Er) have been synthesized and characterized. Both L_1 and L_2 are neutral ligands coordinating through the carbonyl oxygen(s) and the azomethine nitrogen in these complexes. Two perchlorate ions are bidentately coordinated in the complexes of L_1 and one perchlorate ion is bidentately coordinated in the complexes of L_2 . A coordination number of eight is assigned to the metal in both series of complexes.

Keywords : Rare earth perchlorate complexes, 2,3-dimethyl-4-formyl-[2'-(aminomethyl)pyridine]-1-phenyl-3-pyrazolin-5-one, 2,3-dimethyl-4-formyl(benzhydrazide)-1-phenyl-3-pyrazolin-5-one.

Introduction

Rare earth-Schiff base complexes show biological activities¹⁻³ and have pharmacological applications^{4,5} and anti-bacterial^{6,7} as well as anti-inflammatory properties⁸. The special spectroscopic and magnetic properties of lanthanide complexes have prompted their uses as luminescent probes, NMR shift reagents and as MRI agents⁹⁻¹¹. Here we report the synthesis and characterization of two new pyrazolone derived Schiff bases and its complexes with yttrium and some lanthanide perchlorates. The ligands (L_1 and L_2) (Figs. 1 and 2) and the complexes are ex-

Fig. 1. 2,3-Dimethyl-4-formyl-[2'-(aminomethyl)pyridine]-1-phenyl-3-pyrazolin-5-one (L_1).

Fig. 2. 2,3-Dimethyl-4-formyl(benzhydrazide)-1-phenyl-3-pyrazolin-5-one (L_2).

pected to have physiological importance.

Experimental

Antipyrine-4-carboxaldehyde, benzhydrazide and 2-(aminomethyl)pyridine were purchased from Aldrich, USA. Yttrium and lanthanide perchlorates were prepared by dissolving the respective oxides (99.9%) (Rare Earths Ltd., Kerala or Aldrich, USA) in 60% AR perchloric acid (Merck). The crystals of the metal perchlorates were obtained by evaporating the solution using a steam bath. The solvents used were either GPR or AR grade (Merck, India; BDH, India or SRL, India). The Schiff bases L_1 and L_2 were analyzed for the elements carbon, hydrogen

and nitrogen on a Heraeus CHNO rapid analyzer. The metal was estimated gravimetrically as oxides¹⁶ and the perchlorate content by Kurz method¹⁷. The molar conductances in DMF, methanol and nitrobenzene (10^{-3} M solutions) were measured at room temperature using a Toshniwal conductivity bridge with a dip-type cell of platinum electrodes (cell constant 1.1008). The IR spectrum of the Schiff bases and the complexes were recorded in the range $4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ on a Shimadzu IR 470 spectrophotometer. The electronic spectra in solid state (paste with Nujol) and in solution (10^{-3} M DMF and methanol) were recorded in the range $200\text{--}1100\text{ nm}$ on a Shimadzu UV 160A spectrophotometer. The ^1H NMR and ^{13}C NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker DRX-500 spectrometer using $\text{DMSO-}d_6$ as solvent.

Preparation of the ligands :

2,3-Dimethyl-4-formyl-[2-(aminomethyl)pyridine]-1-phenyl-3-pyrazoline-5-one (L_1) :

To a boiling solution of 10 mmol of 2-(aminomethyl)pyridine (1.0815 g) in ethanol (20 mL), 10 mmol of antipyrine-4-carboxaldehyde (2.1624 g) in ethanol (30 mL) was added and refluxed on a steam bath for about six hours. The precipitated light brown crystals were filtered and washed with cold ethanol to remove the unreacted reactants, if any. It was then recrystallized from ethyl acetate and dried over phosphorus(V)oxide under vacuum. The purity was checked by TLC, infrared spectrum and elemental analyses.

2,3-Dimethyl-4-formyl(benzhydrazide)-1-phenyl-3-pyrazolin-5-one (L_2) :

A quantity of 10 mmol of benzhydrazide (1.3615 g) in ethanol (20 ml) was mixed with few drops of A.R. HCl to maintain the pH at 6 and refluxed on a steam bath. 10 mmol of antipyrine-4-carboxaldehyde (2.1624 g) in ethanol (30 ml) was added to the above solution and refluxed for about 6 h. The pale yellow crystals obtained after cooling were washed with cold ethanol to remove the unreacted reactants, if any. It was then recrystallised from ethyl acetate and dried over phosphorus(V)oxide under reduced pressure. The purity was checked by TLC, infrared spectrum and elemental analyses.

Preparation of the complexes :

Complexes of L_1 :

One mmol of the metal perchlorate in methanol (10

mL) was added to a boiling solution of 2.1 mmol of the ligand (0.6434 g) in ethanol (20 mL) and refluxed in a 100 mL R.B. flask on a steam bath for about six hours. The solid complexes formed on cooling were filtered and washed with hot benzene to remove any excess of the reactants. It was then recrystallised from methanol and dried over phosphorus(V)oxide under vacuum.

Complexes of L_2 :

One mmol of the metal perchlorate in methanol (10 ml) was added to a boiling solution of 2.1 mmol of the Schiff base (0.7022 g) in ethanol (20 ml) and kept under reflux for about 4 h. The crystalline solid complex formed on cooling was filtered and washed with isopropanol and hot benzene subsequently to remove any excess of reactants. It was then recrystallised from methanol and dried over phosphorus(V)oxide under vacuum.

Results and discussion

From the elemental analyses results, the complexes may be formulated as $\text{Ln}(\text{L}_1)_2(\text{ClO}_4)_3$ and $\text{Ln}(\text{L}_2)_2(\text{ClO}_4)_3$ ($\text{Ln} = \text{Y, La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd, Dy, Ho}$ or Er). They are non-hygroscopic solids soluble in acetone, DMF, DMSO, ethanol, isopropanol, methanol and nitrobenzene but insoluble in acetonitrile, benzene, carbon tetrachloride, chloroform, ethyl acetate, toluene and water.

The observed values of the electrical conductance of yttrium and lanthanide perchlorate complexes of L_1 and L_2 in three non aqueous solvents, viz. DMF, methanol and nitrobenzene are in good agreement with the results of Geary¹⁸ and suggest 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 electrolytic behaviors for the complexes of L_1 and L_2 respectively. Thus the complexes may be formulated as :

($\text{Ln} = \text{Y, La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd, Dy, Ho}$ or Er)

IR spectra :

The IR spectrum of L_1 exhibits a strong absorption at 1660 cm^{-1} corresponding to the stretching vibration of the pyrazolone carbonyl group¹⁹⁻²¹. The band observed at 1562 cm^{-1} is attributed to the azomethine ($\text{C}=\text{N}$) stretching vibrations^{19,22}. The shift of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ and $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ frequencies to around 1615 and 1588 cm^{-1} respectively in the complexes indicates the chelation of the

ligand through the carbonyl oxygen and the azomethine nitrogen^{20,21}. Furthermore, the complexes show bands corresponding to both coordinated and ionic perchlorates. The strong band at 1080–1085 cm^{-1} is assigned to the $\nu_3(T_d)$ vibration^{23–25} of the ionic perchlorates. The ν_4 vibration of ionic perchlorate group gives a broad band around 628 cm^{-1} and is due to the coupling of it with the ν_7 vibration of the bidentate perchlorate group^{24,26}. The bands observed at 1132–1140, 1108–1112, 1030–1036 and 940–942 cm^{-1} are due the $\nu_8(B_1)$, $\nu_6(B_1)$, $\nu_1(A_1)$ and $\nu_2(A_1)$ vibrations respectively of the perchlorate ion having C_{2v} symmetry, which indicate the presence of bidentately coordinated perchlorates^{15,27}. The $\nu(M-O)$ and $\nu(M-N)$ stretching vibrations are observed around 552 and 476 cm^{-1} respectively¹⁸.

The Schiff base L_2 shows two strong absorption bands at 1668 and 1628 cm^{-1} which are attributed to the $C=O_{(19)}$ and $C=O_{(18)}$ stretching vibrations respectively^{19–21}. In complexes, these bands shifted to 1635 and 1575 cm^{-1} indicating the coordination of both the carbonyl oxygens. The band at 1565 cm^{-1} is ascribed to $C=N$ stretching vibration^{13–15} in L_2 . In complexes, it shifts to ~ 1555 cm^{-1} showing the coordination of azomethine nitrogen. Thus the ligand appears to be tridentate. The complexes show the IR bands corresponding to both coordinated and ionic perchlorates. The strong band at 1082–1088 cm^{-1} is assigned to the ν_3 vibration of the ionic perchlorate^{23–25}. The ν_4 vibration of ionic perchlorate gives a broad band

around 625 cm^{-1} and is due to the coupling of it with the ν_7 vibration of the bidentate perchlorate group^{24,26}. The bands observed at 1140–1148, 1114–1120, 1020–1026 and 920–928 cm^{-1} are due the ν_8 , ν_6 , ν_1 and ν_2 vibrations respectively of the perchlorate having C_{2v} symmetry, which indicate the presence of bidentately coordinated perchlorate^{15,27}. The $\nu(M-O)$ and $\nu(M-N)$ stretching vibrations are observed around 552 and 476 cm^{-1} respectively¹⁸.

Electronic spectra :

The absorption spectrum of the ligand L_1 shows two maxima at 40387 and 29832 cm^{-1} which corresponds to $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions respectively¹⁹. In complexes, these bands shift to the regions 39760–40010 and 25900–27328 cm^{-1} respectively. The $f-f$ bands are observed only in the case of Pr^{III} , Nd^{III} , Sm^{III} , Dy^{III} , Ho^{III} and Er^{III} complexes and for other lanthanide complexes, the bands could not be identified as they are presumably masked by the ligand charge transfer transitions^{28–30}. The band shift compared to those of aqua ions [$\Delta\nu = \nu_{(\text{com})} - \nu_{(\text{aquo})}$] may be used as a measure of the metal-ligand covalent bonding²⁸. The $f-f$ transition frequencies along with tentative assignments^{15,29} are given in Table 1. Calculations using $\Delta\nu$ suggest weak covalent character to the metal-ligand bond. The spectral features of complexes are similar both in the solid state and in solution (DMF and methanol), indicating the identical stoichiometry and coordination number in solid as well as in solution phase. Similar observations were obtained with L_2 .

Table 1. $f-f$ Transitions of the perchlorate complexes of Pr, Nd, Sm, Dy, Ho and Er with L_1

Complex	Abs. max (cm^{-1})	Molar		Tentative assignments	Bonding parameters
		extinction			
		coefficients ^a (ϵ)			
		DMF	MeOH		
[Pr(L_1) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂](ClO ₄)	22525	14.86	10.90	$^3H_4 \rightarrow ^3P_2$	$\beta = 0.9991$
	21277	10.7	6.14	$^3H_4 \rightarrow ^3P_1$	$b^{1/2} = 0.0212$
	20703	7.8	6.08	$^3H_4 \rightarrow ^3P_0$	$\delta = 0.0900$
	16835	2.7	4.51	$^3H_4 \rightarrow ^1D_2$	$\eta = 0.0005$
[Nd(L_1) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂](ClO ₄)	19493	15.56	11.69	$^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow ^4G_{9/2}$	$\beta = 0.9981$
	13550	16.22	16.50	$^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow ^4F_{7/2}$	$b^{1/2} = 0.0308$
	12547	9.10	10.03	$^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow ^4F_{5/2}$	$\delta = 0.1904$
	11507	7.96	8.17	$^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow ^4F_{3/2}$	$\eta = 0.0010$
[Sm(L_1) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂](ClO ₄)	24026	4.66	6.62	$^6H_{5/2} \rightarrow (^6P, ^4P)_{5/2}$	$\beta = 0.9980$
	21053	5.56	8.05	$^6H_{5/2} \rightarrow ^4I_{11/2}$	$b^{1/2} = 0.0316$
	20618	9.11	14.44	$^6H_{5/2} \rightarrow ^4M_{15/2}$	$\delta = 0.2004$
	10493	16.07	15.87	$^4I_{9/2} \rightarrow ^4F_{11/2}$	$\eta = 0.0009$

					Table-1 (contd.)
[Dy(L ₁) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂](ClO ₄)	25906	2.07	3.84	⁶ H _{5/2} → ⁴ I _{13/2}	β = 0.9984
	22173	2.93	3.65	⁶ H _{5/2} → ⁴ I _{15/2}	b ^{1/2} = 0.0283
	13210	1.98	18.11	⁶ H _{15/2} → ⁶ F _{3/2}	δ = 0.1603
	12422	7.12	6.07	⁶ H _{15/2} → ⁶ F _{5/2}	η = 0.0008
	11013	3.75	5.73	⁶ H _{15/2} → ⁶ F _{7/2}	
[Ho(L ₁) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂](ClO ₄)	23697	18.14	11.30	⁵ I ₈ → (⁵ G ₃ , ³ G) ₅	β = 0.9958
	22026	10.57	14.87	⁵ I ₈ → ⁵ G ₅	b ^{1/2} = 0.0458
	21088	14.39	15.01	⁵ I ₈ → ⁵ F ₂	δ = 0.4218
	20534	15.33	11.10	⁵ I ₈ → ⁵ F ₃	η = 0.0021
	18552	8.00	6.73	⁵ I ₈ → ⁵ F ₄	
[Er(L ₁) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂](ClO ₄)	15480	7.20	9.98	⁵ I ₈ → ⁵ F ₅	
	24510	18.23	15.77	⁴ I _{15/2} → (² G, ⁴ F) _{9/2}	β = 0.9958
	22290	12.80	11.10	⁴ I _{15/2} → ⁴ F _{5/2}	b ^{1/2} = 0.0458
	20547	4.62	5.19	⁴ I _{15/2} → ⁴ F _{7/2}	δ = 0.4218
	19285	4.66	5.34	⁴ I _{15/2} → ⁴ H _{11/2}	η = 0.0021
	18598	6.04	7.96	⁴ I _{15/2} → ⁴ S _{3/2}	
	15400	3.66	2.33	⁴ I _{15/2} → ⁴ F _{9/2}	
10294	3.76	4.58	⁴ I _{15/2} → ⁴ I _{11/2}		

^aL mol⁻¹ cm.

The *f-f* bands with L₂ complexes were observed only in the case of Pr^{III}, Nd^{III}, Sm^{III}, Dy^{III}, Ho^{III} and Er^{III} complexes. The *f-f* transition frequencies along with tentative assignments^{15,30} and the covalency parameters are given in Table 2. It is found that the values of β are less than unity and those of η and b^{1/2} are positive. These results, as before, suggest weak covalent character of the metal-ligand bond.

¹H NMR spectra :

The ¹H NMR resonance signals of the ligand L₁ and its yttrium as well as lanthanum perchlorate complexes at room temperature are presented in Table 3 along with their assignments indicating the coordination of azomethine nitrogen and carbonyl oxygen^{30,31}.

The ¹H NMR spectrum of L₂ with assignments are

Table 2. *f-f* Transitions of the perchlorate complexes of Pr, Nd, Sm, Dy, Ho and Er with L₂

Complex	Abs. max (cm ⁻¹)	Molar		Tentative assignments	Bonding parameters
		extinction			
		coefficients ^a (ε)			
		DMF	MeOH		
[Pr(L ₂) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	22422	12.46	12.39	³ H ₄ → ³ P ₂	β = 0.9975
	21186	6.77	6.74	³ H ₄ → ³ P ₁	b ^{1/2} = 0.0354
	20747	5.98	5.94	³ H ₄ → ³ P ₀	δ = 0.2506
	16835	3.27	3.14	³ H ₄ → ¹ D ₂	η = 0.0013
[Nd(L ₂) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂](ClO ₄) ₂	21142	10.59	10.55	⁴ I _{9/2} → ⁴ G _{9/2}	β = 0.9987
	19084	11.04	11.08	⁴ I _{9/2} → ⁴ G _{7/2}	b ^{1/2} = 0.0255
	17331	8.76	8.76	⁴ I _{9/2} → ⁴ G _{7/2}	δ = 0.1302
	13441	17.21	17.20	⁴ I _{9/2} → ⁴ F _{7/2}	η = 0.0007
	12547	9.11	9.13	⁴ I _{9/2} → ⁴ F _{5/2}	
	11507	7.66	7.67	⁴ I _{9/2} → ⁴ F _{3/2}	

						Table-2 (contd.)
[Sm(L ₂) ₂ (ClO ₄)](ClO ₄) ₂	22321	2.06	2.06	⁶ H _{5/2} → ⁴ M _{17/2}	β = 0.9978	
	21053	8.46	8.48	⁶ H _{5/2} → ⁴ I _{11/2}	b ^{1/2} = 0.0317	
	20576	16.27	16.27	⁶ H _{5/2} → ⁴ M _{15/2}	δ = 0.2205	
					η = 0.0011	
[Dy(L ₂) ₂ (ClO ₄)](ClO ₄) ₂	12422	1.57	1.54	⁶ H _{15/2} → ⁶ F _{3/2}	β = 0.9981	
	11001	2.93	2.91	⁶ H _{15/2} → ⁶ F _{5/2}	b ^{1/2} = 0.0308	
	10142	3.74	3.73	⁶ H _{15/2} → ⁶ F _{7/2}	δ = 0.1904	
					η = 0.0009	
[Ho(L ₂) ₂ (ClO ₄)](ClO ₄) ₂	22222	15.80	15.84	⁵ I ₈ → ⁵ F ₁	β = 0.9962	
	21097	14.35	14.35	⁵ I ₈ → ⁵ F ₂	b ^{1/2} = 0.0019	
	20618	10.06	10.05	⁵ I ₈ → ⁵ F ₃	δ = 0.3814	
	18485	4.15	4.13	⁵ I ₈ → ⁵ F ₄	η = 0.0019	
	15504	6.02	6.04	⁵ I ₈ → ⁵ F ₅		
[Er(L ₂) ₂ (ClO ₄)](ClO ₄) ₂	22321	2.95	2.95	⁵ I _{15/2} → ⁴ F _{3/2}	β = 0.9973	
	22026	13.10	13.11	⁴ I _{15/2} → ⁴ F _{5/2}	b ^{1/2} = 0.0367	
	20367	2.02	2.02	⁴ I _{15/2} → ⁴ F _{7/2}	δ = 0.2707	
	19231	4.66	4.64	⁴ I _{15/2} → ⁴ H _{11/2}	η = 0.0014	
	18450	5.77	5.76	⁴ I _{15/2} → ⁴ S _{3/2}		
	15175	1.35	1.34	⁴ I _{15/2} → ⁴ F _{9/2}		

^aL mol⁻¹ cm.Table 3. ¹H NMR spectral data of L₁ and its complexes with yttrium and lanthanum perchlorates

L ₁		[Y(L ₁) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂](ClO ₄)		[Y(L ₁) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂](ClO ₄)		Assignment
B	I	B	I	B	I	
2.08	19.10	2.08	38.20	2.08	38.20	C—CH ₃
3.12	19.10	3.12	38.20	3.12	38.20	N—CH ₃
4.58	1.42	4.70	3.69	4.70	3.69	N—CH ₂ —C
7.89	3.19	5.89	12.73	5.90	12.73	
7.67	1.91	7.62	3.02	7.61	3.02	
7.46	1.37	7.20	2.42	7.20	2.42	
7.23	0.92	7.21	3.42	7.21	3.42	
7.46	0.32	7.22	3.09	7.20	3.12	
7.67	1.93	7.62	3.02	7.61	3.02	
8.67	0.40	8.69	0.80	8.69	0.80	
7.14	0.44	7.14	0.85	7.14	0.85	
7.74	0.43	7.74	0.85	7.74	0.85	
7.21	0.84	7.40	0.91	7.40	0.91	

B = band position; I = intensity.

given in Table 4. The coordination through azomethine nitrogen³¹ is confirmed since the (-N=C-H) singlet at 8.38 ppm is shifted to a down field, i.e. to 8.04 ppm in yttrium and lanthanum complexes. The broad multiplets in the region 7.23–7.67 ppm and 7.53–7.79 ppm are at-

tributable to the phenyl protons of pyrazolone and hydrazide moieties respectively and their shifts to the regions 7.20–7.62 ppm and 7.54–7.98 ppm respectively credit the coordination of both the carbonyl oxygens which are adjacent to the phenyl rings and strong electron

Table 4. ¹H NMR spectral data of L₂ and its yttrium and lanthanum perchlorate complexes

L ₁		[Y(L ₂) ₂ (ClO ₄)](ClO ₄) ₂		[Y(L ₂) ₂ (ClO ₄)](ClO ₄) ₂		Assignment
B	I	B	I	B	I	
2.53	19.1	2.53	38.20	2.53	38.20	
	0					
3.35	19.1	3.35	38.20	3.35	38.20	
	0					
8.38	6.39	8.04	12.73	8.04	12.75	
11.29	6.37	8.08	0.25	8.10	0.33	
7.67	1.91	7.62	3.02	7.62	3.02	
7.46	1.37	7.20	2.42	7.20	2.42	
7.23	0.92	7.21	3.42	7.21	3.42	
7.46	1.33	7.22	3.09	7.22	3.09	
7.67	1.92	7.62	3.02	7.62	3.02	
7.76	2.20	7.98	3.23	7.98	3.23	
7.79	2.50	7.67	2.15	7.67	2.15	
7.53	0.67	7.54	2.07	7.54	2.07	
7.79	2.39	7.65	2.20	7.65	2.20	
7.77	1.43	7.98	3.45	7.98	3.45	

B = band position; I = intensity.

Table 5. ¹³C NMR spectral data of L₁ and its yttrium and lanthanum perchlorate complexes

L ₁	[Y(L ₁) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂](ClO ₄)	[La(L ₁) ₂ (ClO ₄) ₂](ClO ₄)	Assignment
8.13	8.13	8.13	
37.62	37.62	37.62	
45.00	69.01	69.01	
161.30	161.30	161.30	
109.20	100.44	100.44	
164.80	169.30	169.30	
166.73	147.42	147.42	
147.26	147.26	147.26	
123.28	125.31	125.31	
130.69	127.62	127.62	
126.47	126.61	126.61	
130.69	127.62	127.62	
123.28	125.31	125.31	
156.76	154.98	154.98	
149.18	149.18	149.18	
125.25	125.25	125.25	
136.47	136.47	136.47	
123.44	129.08	129.08	

Table 6. ^{13}C NMR spectral data of L_2 and its yttrium and lanthanum perchlorate complexes

L_1	$[\text{Y}(\text{L}_2)_2(\text{ClO}_4)](\text{ClO}_4)_2$	$[\text{La}(\text{L}_2)_2(\text{ClO}_4)](\text{ClO}_4)_2$	Assignment
8.13	8.13	8.13	$\text{C}-\text{C}_{13}^{\text{H}_3}$
37.62	37.60	37.60	$\text{N}-\text{C}_{12}^{\text{H}_3}$
144.35	124.84	124.87	$\text{N}=\text{C}_{14}=\text{H}$
161.30	161.30	161.30	
109.20	100.01	100.01	
164.80	166.32	166.32	
147.26	147.26	147.26	
123.28	125.31	125.31	
130.69	127.62	127.62	
126.47	126.61	126.61	
130.69	127.62	127.62	
123.28	125.31	125.31	
168.47	164.43	164.45	
132.49	131.24	131.24	
127.67	138.32	138.32	
129.35	129.97	129.97	
134.47	133.04	133.04	
129.35	129.97	129.97	
127.67	138.32	138.32	

^aCorresponding to the signals at 37.92–41.08 ppm of $\text{DMSO}-d_6$.

withdrawing groups³⁰.

^{13}C NMR spectra :

The ^{13}C NMR of L_1 as well as its yttrium and lanthanide complexes are presented in Table 5. The reso-

nance signal at 166.73 ppm in L_1 due to $\text{C}_{(14)}$ is shifted to 147.42 ppm in complexes showing the coordination of azomethine nitrogen¹⁰ and the shifts of $\text{C}_{(4)}$ and $\text{C}_{(5)}$ to 100.44 and 169.30 ppm respectively indicate the coordi-

Fig. 3. $[\text{Ln}(\text{L}_1)_2(\text{ClO}_4)_2](\text{ClO}_4)$ ($\text{Ln} = \text{Y, La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd, Dy, Ho}$ or Er).

Fig. 4. $[\text{Ln}(\text{L}_2)_2(\text{ClO}_4)_2](\text{ClO}_4)_2$ ($\text{Ln} = \text{Y, La, Pr, Nd, Sm, Eu, Gd, Dy, Ho}$ or Er).

nation of ring carbonyl oxygen.

The ^{13}C NMR of L_2 as well as its yttrium and lanthanide perchlorate complexes are presented in Table 6 and show the coordination of azomethine [$\text{C}_{(14)}$] nitrogen¹⁰.

On the basis of analytical and spectral data the tentative structure of the complexes may be assigned as follows (Figs. 3 and 4).

Acknowledgement

The authors are indebted to Mahatma Gandhi University, Kottayam, Kerala, India, for providing the facilities and awarding a Junior Research Fellowship to one of us (GAK). We thank the Heads of the Regional Sophisticated Instrumentation Centre, Indian Institute of Technology, Chennai; Regional Research Laboratory, Thiruvananthapuram and Tata Institute of Fundamental Research, Mumbai, India for some instrumental analyses. Also, we wish to express our heartfelt thanks to Dr. Siby Joseph and Dr. N. T. Madhu for some fruitful discussions.

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